

Supplementary figure 1: Percentage of reads per cell mapped to the genome of *M.musculus* or *T. gondii* (ME49). Dark color (blue) indicates mouse as species, light color (orange) indicates *T. gondii* (left panel). Distribution of unique *T. gondii* specific molecules across infection conditions (strain and time point) in percent per cell (right panel).

Supplementary figure 2: Distribution of original infection conditions across identified clusters in murine data (M1-M9). For each cluster (M1-M9) the percentage of cells belonging to the original condition is shown in a stacked barplot from 0 to 100%. Each color signifies a different condition depicted on the legend (right).

Supplementary figure 3: Gene expression signature of identified BMDC subpopulations. Heatmap depicting averaged gene expression profiles of cells identified as GM-DC and GM-Mac across murine clusters M1-M9. Genes identified as markers for each cell type as well as CD surface marker genes are highlighted with a black line. High expression is shown in yellow, while low expression is shown in dark purple.

Supplementary figure 4: Cell cycle scoring of BMDCs infected with *T. gondii* parasites.

UMAP projection of cells grouped by assigned cell cycle phase using the *CellCycleScoring* function in Seurat (methods).

Supplementary figure 5: Expression profiles of selected genes encoding cell cycle regulation genes (cyclins and kinases). **a** Density plot exhibiting expression values of gene expression for *Ccnd2* (left), *Ccne1* and *Ccne2* encoding CyclinD2, CyclinE1 and CyclinE2 across murine clusters. Density distributions are colored based on the cluster identity as seen in the legend (right). **b** Density plot exhibiting expression values of gene expression for *Cdk1* (left), *Cdk2* (left middle), *Cdk4* (right middle) and *Cdk6* (right) encoding cyclin depending kinases corresponding phosphorylating cyclins during cell cycle progression. Density distributions are colored based on the cluster identity as seen in the legend (right).

a

b

Supplementary figure 8: Correlated genes of extended *T. gondii* network 2 (ETGN2).
 Visualization of Pearson correlation coefficients between genes in extended *T. gondii* ETGN 2. Correlation values are shown in a gradient from most negative values in dark purple to most positive values in yellow (light).

Supplementary figure 9: Effect of cell cycle regression on clustering of *T. gondii* parasites. UMAP projection of cells grouped by assigned replication state of the parasite using a modified version of the CellCycleScoring function in Seurat and known G1 and S/M transcription profiles of the parasite (methods) before regression of the assigned cell cycle state (left panel). UMAP projection of cells grouped by assigned replication state of the parasite using a modified version of the CellCycleScoring function in Seurat and known G1 and S/M transcription profiles of the parasite (methods) after regression of the assigned cell cycle state (right panel).

Supplementary figure 10: Differentially expressed genes between identified *T. gondii* clusters. Heatmap depicting averaged gene expression of *T. gondii* marker genes of identified clusters. High expression is shown in yellow, while low expression is shown in dark purple.

Supplementary figure 11: Heatmap depicting differentially expressed *T. gondii* genes grouped by *T. gondii* clusters (Tg1- Tg4) across host clusters exhibiting infection (M1-M7). Cell type annotations of host clusters are indicated by turquoise (GM-DC) and purple (GM-Mac). Averaged gene expression is shown in a color gradient from low expression (dark purple) to high expression (yellow). The *T. gondii* clusters are represented in the colors selected for each cluster

Supplementary figure 12: Heatmap depicting differentially expressed *T. gondii* genes of *T. gondii* cluster Tg5 across host clusters exhibiting infection (M1-M7). Cell type annotations of host clusters are indicated by turquoise (GM-DC) and purple (GM-Mac). Averaged gene expression is shown in a color gradient from low expression (dark purple) to high expression (yellow). The *T. gondii* clusters are represented in the colors selected for each cluster

